

Al- Salam University College 2016/ 2017
English Department
Third Class
Subject: Structural Grammar
Al Salam University Collge

Final Exam
Time: 3 Hours
Teacher: Alhan Tariq

Note: Answer FIVE questions only

Q.1 Show the immediate constituents of the following words: (10 Marks)

1. helpless
2. embodiment
3. unlawful
4. reimbursements
5. preprofessional

Q.2 Identify whether the words underlined in the following sentences are compound or grammatical structures: (10 Marks)

1. Jim's new car is a hardtop.
2. she has a strong hold on him.
3. George found his father- in- law.
4. Henry is a designing teacher. (designing is with rising- falling intonation, teacher with falling rising intonation)
5. They bought it on the black market.

Q.3 Indicate the process of word formation represented by each of the following words: (10 Marks)

1. administration
2. tick- tick
3. hiss
4. OPEC
5. smog

Q.4 Derive nouns from the following words: (10 Marks)

1. help
2. complain
3. wise
4. friend
5. contemplate
6. accept
7. coward
8. piano
9. true
10. violent

Q.5 Write grammatical sentences with the following: (10 Marks)

1. compound preposition
2. periphrastic auxiliary do
3. substitute noun
4. a qualifier that modifies an adjective
5. an article

Q.6 Show the number of morphemes each of the following words contain: (10 Marks)

1. unforgettable
2. enlargement
3. malformations
4. refertilize
5. started

Good Luck

Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim

Note: Answer FIVE questions only

Q.1 Show the immediate constituents of the following words: (10 Marks)

1. lifelessness
2. gentlemanly
3. cheerful
4. uncomfortable
5. itemized

Q.2 Identify whether the suffixes of the words underlined are ed-verbal, ed-adjectival, ing nominal, ing verbal, ing adjectival, er repetition, er noun, or er comparative (10 Marks)

1. You should read the printed statement.
2. A worried look crossed his face.
3. Old sayings are often half true.
4. A moving elephant is a picture of grace.
5. It was a charming spot.
6. The fighter weighed 100 kgs.
7. The jabber of voices came through the open door.
8. This is a heavier tennis racket than I want.

Q.3 Give the verb forms from the following adjectives: (10 Marks)

1. ripe
2. safe
3. solemn
4. solid
5. idol

Q.4 Show the grammatical structures that imply the following compound words: (10 Marks)

1. quicksand
2. outgo
3. treetop
4. stay- at- home
5. earthquake

Q.5 Give an example for each of the following word formation processes: (10 Marks)

1. reduplication
2. compounding
3. acronymy
4. clipping
5. derivation

Q.6 Underline the part of speech(structure class) in the following sentences: (10 Marks)

1. You are too tired.
2. I feel quite fine, thank you.
3. George sat between the two deans.
4. His is the best plan.
5. I think I can help you.

Good Luck

Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim

First Year

Writing in Paragraphs

Al- Iraqia University

College of Arts

Note: Answer FOUR questions only.

Q.1 Fill in the blanks to complete the following sentences:

1. A sentence is
2. The is the name of your writing.
3. The paragraph is weak or bad if
4. A is a group of words that does not have a subject nor verb or it has either a subject or verb only.
5. A should be placed before the coordinators and, but, so and yet in coordinate sentences.

Q.2 Choose the correct answer to complete the following sentences:

1. A paragraph is strong or weak if it has
 - a. one topic sentence.
 - b. one idea.
 - c. one supporting sentence.
 - d. semi colon.
2. A sentence should start with a
 - a. capital letter.

b. full stop.

c. small letter.

d. semi colon.

3. The adjective can come before the, e.g. the brilliant students.

a. noun

b. verb

c. adverb

d. preposition

4. Brainstorming by free writing means you use

a. words

b. phrases

c. short sentences

d. long sentences

5. Peer reviewing means you hand your writing to your to check it for you.

a. teacher

b. father

c. classmate

d. neighbor

Q.3 Write true if the sentence is correct, and false if it is incorrect of each of the following sentences:

1. Each paragraph should have a topic, supporting and concluding sentences.
2. A topic sentence should be the last sentence of the paragraph
3. In checking, you check whether your writing has a title, sentences are related to the topic, etc.
4. The topic that explains the topic is called supporting sentences.
5. A simple sentence should consist of two sentences combined by and or but.

Q.4 Suggest a topic sentence and concluding sentence for the following paragraph:

Steps to Follow to Use ATM

..... First, you need to insert your card into the machine to begin transaction. Second, type in your PIN. This is typically 4 digits but can be longer. Third, choose a type of transaction. Fourth, enter the transaction amount. Fifth, select your receipt preference. Finally, take your card.

..... .

Q.5 Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe ONE of the following topics:

1. your favourite place

2. you favourite person

Your writing should be about 60 words in length.

Brainstorm and write a descriptive paragraph on a piece of art you like, e.g. painting or sculpture. Your writing should be no more than 60 words in length.

Note: Answer FOUR questions only.

Q.1 Fill in the blanks to complete the following sentences:

1. There are six steps of writing. 1., 2., 3., 4., 5., and 6.
2. Margins means
3. A sentence should start with a and end with
4. There are four types of writing: 1., 2., 3., and 4.
5. The little boy looked so I went to comfort him.

Q.2 Choose the correct answer to complete the following sentences:

1. A coordinate sentence means
 - a. summarizing the whole paragraph.
 - b. developing the whole paragraph.
 - c. telling the reader about the topic.
 - d. explaining the topic sentence.
2. Supporting sentences
 - a. develop your topic sentence.
 - b. restate your topic sentence.
 - c. summarize the whole paragraph.
 - d. tell the reader about the topic of the paragraph.

3. A paragraph is a group of sentences that talk about one certain

- a. idea
- b. phrase
- c. topic
- d. sentence

4. A concluding sentence is the sentence that

- a. develops the topic sentence
- b. summarize the paragraph
- c. explains the topic sentence
- d. restate the topic sentence

5. capitalization is used with

- a. proper nouns
- b. coordinators
- c. articles
- d. demonstratives

Q.3 Write true if the sentence is correct, and false if it is incorrect of each of the following sentences:

- 1. A paragraph is a group of sentences that talks about many topics.
- 2. Title means the space you leave from both sides of your writing.
- 3. The descriptive paragraph tells events in a certain place and time.

4. A comma comes at the end of a sentence.
5. A simple sentence should consist of one subject and one verb.

Q.4 State whether the following paragraph is a good or bad one and give reasons for your answer:

Why do People Lie?

One reason why people lie is to achieve personal power. Achieving personal power is helpful for someone who pretends that he is more confident than he really is. For example, my friend asked me to show him my car. At that time, I did not have any car because I sold it. This is why I asked my cousin to lend me his. When I showed him my cousin's car, I felt confident but embarrassed in front of my friend but I looked down on myself. Even if lying achieves power and confidence, I decided since then not to do so.

Q.5 Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe ONE of the following topics:

- 1. your favourite book,**
- 2. your favourite dish,**

Your writing should be about 60 words in length.

Brainstorm and write a descriptive paragraph on a lucky object, e.g. an object that you think brings luck to your life. Your writing should be no more than 60 words in length.

Note: Answer FOUR questions only.

Q.1 Fill in the blanks to complete the following sentences: (15 Points)

1. A sentence is
2. The is the name of your writing.
3. The paragraph is weak or bad if
4. A is a group of words that does not have a subject nor verb or it has either a subject or verb only.
5. A should be placed before the coordinators and, but, so and yet in coordinate sentences.

Q.2 Choose the correct answer to complete the following sentences:

(15 Points)

1. A paragraph is strong or weak if it has
 - a. one topic sentence.
 - b. one idea.
 - c. one supporting sentence.
 - d. semi colon.
2. A sentence should start with a
 - a. capital letter.
 - b. full stop.
 - c. small letter.
 - d. semi colon.
3. The adjective can come before the, e.g. the brilliant students.
 - a. noun
 - b. verb
 - c. adverb

d. preposition

4. Brainstorming by free writing means you use

a. words

b. phrases

c. short sentences

d. long sentences

5. Peer reviewing means you hand your writing to your to check it for you.

a. teacher

b. father

c. classmate

d. neighbor

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Q.4 Suggest a topic sentence and concluding sentence for the following paragraph: (15 Points)

Steps to Follow to Use ATM

..... First, you need to insert your card into the machine to begin transaction. Second, type in your PIN. This is typically 4 digits but can be longer. Third, choose a type of transaction. Fourth, enter the transaction amount. Fifth, select your receipt preference. Finally, take your card.

Q.5 Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe your favourite place. Your writing should be about 60 words in length. (15 Points)

Good Luck

Instructor: Alhan T. Najim

Answer ALL questions:

Q. Complete the following sentences:

- 1. A Is a group of words that does not have a subject or a verb or neither a subject nor verb.**
- 2. A strong or good paragraph should have and**
- 3. Every topic sentence should have and**
- 4. Examples of coordinators are and**
- 5. An example of descriptive adjectives is friendly, for example**
- 6. Brainstorming by listing means**
- 7. Adjectives can come before nouns, e.g. or after verbs to be or senses verb**
- 8. In titles, all words should be capitalized except,, and**
- 9. Concluding sentences are of four types. They can 1., 2., 3. and 4.**

Q.2 Is this paragraph good or bad? And why?

I had a really bad dream yesterday. I felt bad when I woke up. The drive to work took a long time, and it was so depressing. When I finally go to work, my boss was in a bad mood. Work was just really stressful the whole day. I left to go home later, and I didn't feel like staying at home. I called some people and they were all rude to me. I ended up just doing a stuff around the house. I watched some stuff on TV and fell asleep during a boring show.

Q.3 Develop the following topics to write good topic sentences:

a. Global warming

There are many possible contributing factors to global warming.

b. Dogs

Dogs make wonderful pets because they help you to live longer.

Al Salam University College

Fourth Year

Transformational Grammar

Note: Answer FIVE questions only

Q.1 Identify the three schools of Grammar and clarify the differences among them. (10 Marks)

Q.2 Draw tree diagrams of the following sentences: (10 Marks)

1. Yes, Murphy has been very quiet.
2. The fireman will be having trouble soon.

Q.3 A. Use features to explain why the following sentences are ungrammatical. Then correct the sentences. (Five only)(10 Marks)

1. *The perseverance is a virtue.
2. *He has read book.
3. *Despair dropped to the floor.
4. *The eagle prayed for an hour.
- 5.* My boss elapsed.
- 6.* We vanished the spot.

B. What are the three components of Transformational Grammar? Explain.

Q.4 Transform the following sentences into surface structures using tree diagrams: (10 Marks)

1. not she present look tired
2. not Mary past be friendly
3. not they present have seen me here
4. not no that cat present resemble my sister's cat

Q.5 Answer either A or B of the following question: (10 Marks)

A. 1. Give the deep structure from which the following sentence is derived:

What could the man have been doing?

2. From the deep structure, give the words that are represented by the following symbols:

Aux1, V, M, be, Aux, MV, VP

B. Give the surface structure using a tree diagram and applying the transformations, if applicable, in the order: 1) negative, 2) yes no 3) wh transformation, and 4) do transformation.

1. Q the student past answer det- wh questions
2. Q the wife present can bake NP- wh

Q.6 Answer either A or B of the following questions: (10 Marks)

A What are the transformational processes in Transformational Grammar? Explain with examples.

B. Give the deep structure of the following sentences using tree diagrams (TWO only)

1. Listen to me.
2. Yesterday, I didn't know her address.
3. Someone was telling me a story.

Good Luck

Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim

Al- Salam University College 2016/ 2017
English Department
Fourth Class
Subject: Transformational Grammar

Final Exam
Time: 3 Hours
Teacher: Alhan Tariq

Note: Answer FIVE questions only

Q.1 Identify the three schools of Grammar and explain one of them.(10 Marks)

Q.2 Draw tree diagrams of the following sentences: (10 Marks)

1. My neighbour has seen the dog.
2. John could have been running this morning.

Q.3 Give the formulas of the following sentences, then add or delete as required between brackets, and write the resulting sentences: (10 Marks)

1. I ate then. (add be+ ing)
2. You could have been repairing the clock. (Delete be+ ing)
3. The waitress must be laughing at us. (Add have+ en)
4. We had gone to the window. (Delete have+ en)
5. I could see him well. (Delete can)

Q.4 Define the following terms in Transformational Grammar: (FIVE only)

(10 Marks)

1. PSR Phrase Structure Rules
2. TR Transformational Rules
3. PSTS Phrase Structure Terminal String
4. Concrete Nouns
5. Count Nouns
6. Competence
7. Performance

8. Intermediate Structure

9. Lexical Features

10. Lexicon

Q.5 Give the lexical features of the words underlined(nouns and verbs) in the following sentences: (FIVE only) (10 Marks)

1. Ali drives fast.
2. Mary put the book on the table.
3. The boy was lying on the floor.
4. The book dropped to the floor.
5. The ceiling leaks.
6. The camel is chewing the food.

Q.6 Give the deep structure of the following sentences using tree diagrams: (10 Marks)

1. Are you watching the clouds?
2. What did she want?
3. Don is not writing a letter.
4. We don't jump here.
5. The man is not ready now.

Q.7 Transform the following sentences into surface structures using tree diagrams: (10 Marks)

1. Q Bob will speak Adv p- wh
2. Q not he is going Adv r- wh
3. Q he wrote with NP- wh
4. Q not you have found det- wh book
5. Q she wanted NP- wh

Q.8 Answer either A or B: (10 Marks)

A. What are the four transformational processes in Transformational Grammar? Explain with examples and by using tree diagrams.

B. Transform the following sentences into surface structures using tree diagrams: (Five only)

1. Imp not you will close the door
2. I emailed a letter to my teacher (Indirect object movement)
3. I met my friend in this restaurant (Adverbial movement)
4. Q the bell present be ringing now
5. Q he present be saying NP- wh
6. Q not she arrived on time

Good Luck

Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim

First Year

Al Iraqia University College

Note: Answer FOUR questions only.

Q.1 Fill in the blanks to complete the following sentences: (15 Points)

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2. The is the name of your writing.
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(15 Points)

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a. words

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Q.5 Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe your favourite place. Your writing should be about 60 words in length. (15 Points)

Good Luck

Instructor: Alhan T. Najim

Fourth Year

Transformational Grammar

Al Salam University College

Note: Answer FIVE questions only

Q.1 Identify the three schools of Grammar and explain one of them.(10 Marks)

Q.2 Draw tree diagrams of the following sentences: (10 Marks)

1. My neighbour has seen the dog.
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Q.3 Give the formulas of the following sentences, then add or delete as required between brackets, and write the resulting sentences: (10 Marks)

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Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim

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Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim

First Year

Writing in Paragraphs

Al Iraqia University

Answer ALL questions:

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- 2. A strong or good paragraph should have and**
- 3. Every topic sentence should have and**
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- 5. An example of descriptive adjectives is friendly, for example**
- 6. Brainstorming by listing means**
- 7. Adjectives can come before nouns, e.g. or after verbs to be or senses verb**
- 8. In titles, all words should be capitalized except,, and**
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Q.2 Is this paragraph good or bad? And why?

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Q.3 Develop the following topics to write good topic sentences:

a. Global warming

There are many possible contributing factors to global warming.

b. Dogs

Dogs make wonderful pets because they help you to live longer.

Lebanese French University- Questions for the Monthly Exam

Q.1 Write a paragraph to talk about a job that you like to do. You may make use of the following words to write your paragraph.

A salesman/ out of work/ in work/ arrive at work/ part- time/ get to work/ off work/ go by car, train, etc. / responsible for/ in charge of/ full- time/ part- time.

Q.2 Correct the following sentences:

1. He is in charge with financial reporting.
 2. I'm responsible of the safety of passengers.
 3. I like teamwork. This means I like to work of people.
 4. My brother is sick. I should take some time in work to take care of him.
 5. She like to work part- time job because she has a baby to take care of.
-

Q.3 Do you like to work in shifts/ flexitime/ a nine to five job/ telecommuting (working from home)? Use the following words to write your paragraph

Satisfying/ tiring/ commute to work/ involves working with customers/ solving problems/ enjoy long hours/ involve teamwork.

Q.4 Fill in the blanks:

1. Saman works for a company in Ainkawa. However, he prefers to live on Shaqlawa. He has to ----- to work.
a. get b. commute c. arrive d. manage
 2. There is a lot of work to do before Mawrooz. The company asked the employees to work -----.
a. overtime b. telecommuting c. shifts d permanent
 3. I work as a salesman. My job involves----- with customers.
a. deal b dealing c. dealt d does not deal
 4. Kenar ----- the job as a commercial artist.
a. applied for b. recruited c. headhunted d. worked
 5. Because of the economic crisis. Many people are -----.
a. in work b. out of work c. off work d. work
-

Q.5 Choose the correct words in brackets to replace the words underlined of the following:

1. The company has chosen people for the interview 6 people only.
a. shortlisted b. applied for c. commuted d. worked
2. This job is interesting and gives me many positive feelings.

a. repetitive b. satisfying c. tiring d. dull

3. He works from 8.00 am to 5.00 pm in this company.

a. full- time b. part- time c. night shift teamwork

4. The salary is not that high. He refused the job offer to work for this company.

a. accepted b. turned down c. arrived d. applied for

Q. 6 Fill in the blanks to complete the words:

1. He wanted to apply for this job. He completed the app----- form and sent his CV.

2. In order to re-----t people, many people are shortlisted.

3. The company e-----loys highly- skilled people for this job.

4. He is looking for another job. His job is a tem-----rary one.

5. This job involves doing the same things again. It is re-----tive.

Q.7 Complete the following:

1. Nergis is a secretary. She -----from Lebanese French University this year.

a. is graduated b. graduated c. graduate d. graduating

2. He studied Accounting in Cihan College. He ----- as an accountant.

a. qualified b. is qualified c. qualifying d. qualify

3. He works as a brain surgeon for Rezgari hospital and he is very famous in Kurdistan. He is -----.

a. unskilled b. highly- skilled c. skilled d. semi- skilled

Q.8 Match the following:

1. He works from 5 pm to 8 pm.

A. They like to work with other people.

2. Because he is so talented

B. They have shortlisted him.

3. He made an application

C. It involves long hours.

4. This job is tiring

D. he has a part- time job.

5. Those people are team players

E. sending his CV and a covering letter

Q.9 You were looking for a job. Finally, you found. Write about the stages of your recruitment. Make use of the following words:

Jobs website/ a covering letter/ application form/ CV/ recruited me/ background of the applicant/ work experience/ shortlist/ referees/ offer the job.

Q. 10 Fill in the blanks using the correct words from a, b, c, and d.

1. The hotels in summer are very busy. This is why workers do.....

a. overtime b. commute c. full- time d. application

2. She is a saleswoman in a luxury shop in Royal Mall. She get a basic salary, plus -----.

a. application form b. commission c. recruitment d. work experience

3. There is a vacancy for car- cleaners. They need ----- people for this job.

a. unskilled b. skilled c. semi- skilled d. highly- skilled

4. They have good qualifications to work for this job. They just graduated. However, they don't have any -----.

a. work experience b. degree c. teamwork d. recruit.

Q.11 Match between

- | | |
|--|--------------------------------------|
| 1. If the worker is forced to leave the organization | A. he is telecommuting |
| 2. He is working from home. | B. He works in a planned way. |
| 3. He is so methodical and organized | C. He should receive compensation. |
| 4. Some executives are with high pay and benefits | D. I get a bonus. |
| 5. If I pay more than a particular amount a year, | E. They are referred to as fat cats. |
| 6. Beside my basic salary in this shop, | F. I get a commission. |

Q. 12 Describe a job of sports product salesman or computer salesman that you would like to have. Make use of the following words:

Computer literate/ talented/ numerate/ team player.

Q. 13 Use the following words in complete sentences:

1. semi- skilled
2. salary
3. Applied for
4. computer- literate
5. deal with

Q. 14 Complete the following sentences choosing from a, b, c, and d of the following sentences:

1. Workers stop working. This means they have -----
a. a strike b. referee c. bonus d. shifts
2. The people who work in a company are called -----.
a. recruit b. workforce c. labor union d. administration
3. In Iraq, the worker stops working at the age of 65, so he can take his -----
a. pension b. bonus c. commission d. package
4. Companies with temporary contracts expect -----
a. flexibility b. redundancy c. efficiency d. head office

Q. 15 Complete the following sentences:

1. If people are treated differently from each other in an unfair way, they are said to be-----

a. employed b. discriminated against c. headhunted d. shortlisted
2. When the manager uses his position of power to hurt or threaten the employee, he -----
the employee.
a. bullies b. work with c. commutes d. supports

Q. 16 Make sentences with

Perks/ bonus/ semi- skilled/ freelancers/ sacked(fired)/ resist

Q. 17 Match the following

- | | |
|---|--|
| 1. passive smoking | a. There are all these problems, but no one is trained to give medical assistance. |
| 2. Fire hazards | b. I do a lot of data entry, and recently I've started getting really bad pains in my wrists. |
| 3. repetitive strain injury or RIS | c. My doctor says there's something wrong with my lungs but I've never smoked. |
| 4. dangerous machinery | d. There's all this waste paper, but there is no fire extinguishers in the building. |
| 5. First aid | e. There are no safety guards on the machines. You could get easily get your hand caught. |

Q. 18 Draw a management organigram that is followed in UK.

Q. 19 Match between the two columns

- | | |
|--|-----------------------------------|
| 1. Meet with advertising agency to discuss new advertisements for the company's holidays. | A. finance director |
| 2. Study possible new holiday destinations in detail. | B. marketing director |
| 3. Analyse last year's profits relation to the previous year. | C. Human resource director |
| 4. Contact newspaper to advertise new jobs. | D. research director |

Q.20 Write the verbs of the following nouns:

Retirement
Demotion
Dismissal
Termination

Q21 Write the adjectives of the following nouns:

seniority
Freelancer
Redundancy
Insecurity
Flexibility

Q. 22 Who's the most famous entrepreneur in your country? What is he or she famous for?

Q.23 Complete the following (to/ to/ at/ in)

Rebecca lives in London and works in public relations. She leaves home for work at 7:30 am. She drives -----work. The traffic is often bad and she worries about getting ----- work

late, but she usually arrives ----- work at around 9. She loves what she does and glad to be ----- work.

Q. 24 What type of work do you like to have?

Q. 25 Match between the two columns:

- | | |
|--|--|
| 1. work in shifts | a. a designer in a website design company. Has to be in the office but decides when she wants to start and finish work each day. |
| 2. work under a flexitime system | b. a construction worker in a building site where work goes on 24 hours. |
| 3. clock in and out at the same time everyday. | c. An office worker in a large traditional manufacturing company. |

Q. 26 Match between the two columns to decide what kind of people are the following:

- | | |
|-------------------|-------------------|
| 1. Teacher | a. skilled |
| 2. a bus driver | b. highly skilled |
| 3. office manager | c. semi- skilled |
| 4. car designers | d. highly skilled |
| 5. airport pilot | e. skilled |

Q. 27 Make sentences with the following:

Computer literate

Motivated

Systematic

Numerate

Q. 28 Edizionic Fenice is a big magazine publishing company. I was director of a monthly magazine called Casa 2 Giradino.

Then, Fenice was bought by an international publishing group. We had to have regular performance 1. ----- (review/ reviews/ reviewer) with one of the new managers. After a few months, they started laying staff 2. ----- (off/ on/ out). Our own journalists were put on temporary 3. ----- (contracts/ contractual/ contracting) or replaced by 4. ----- (freelancer/ freelancers/ freelanced).

Q. 29 Decide whether these advertisements talk about a part- time job, a full- time job, a temporary job, a permanent job.

1. Librarian required for public library: afternoons 2-6.
2. Teacher needed for summer course. 1 to 31 August.
3. Lawyer wanted for law- firm long hours. 4 weeks holiday per year.

Q. 30 How many ways of working do we have? Identify one only and give examples.

Q. 31 How many types of jobs do we have? Give examples.

Q. 33 State five words to describe the right person for the job.

Q. 34 Identify some benefits that the worker gets when he works, that is the company offers when he starts working).

Q. 35 What do we mean by discrimination? Give an example.

Q. 36 What is the difference between white- collar and blue- collar workers?

Q. 37 In order to ensure the safety of work places, like offices and factories, health and safety inspectors check health and safety issues. Identify three issues only.

Q. 38 Identify two entrepreneurs you' ve heard about.

Q. 39 Do you prefer full- time work or part- time work? Why?

Q. 40 Talk about any job you like to do. Why?

Q. 41 Match between the two columns:

1.My work involves travelling a lot.

I enjoy dealing with customers.

It can sometimes be very dangerous to us and other passengers.

2.My job involves getting up early in the morning.

I walk two or three miles every day.

3.There is a lot of team work between the developers.

It's very satisfying to write a program that works.

A. flight attendant

B. software developer.

C. postman.

LFU

Business Administration

Q1. Encircle the best answer from (a), (b), (c), or (d) of the following to complete the sentences:

1. Rebecca drives to work, but the traffic is often bad and she worries to get..... work late.

- a. to b. from c. on d. for

2. A lawyer is wanted for a law firm to work long hours from 8am- 3pm, 6 days a week, 4 weeks holiday per year. It is a job.

- a. part- time b. temporary c. permanent d. night shift

3. Because of the economic crisis nowadays, many people cannot find jobs. They are

- a. in work b. off work c. out of work d. at work

4. Ivan does not like to work from home. She enjoys with customers.

- a. dealt b. dealing c. deal d. worked

5. I work in London but prefer living outside the city. I to work every day.

- a. commute b. telecommute c. apply d. offer

6. are previous employers, teachers that the candidates have named in their applications.

- a. Applicants b. Referees c. Headhunters d. Recruiters

7. Hazar made an....., sending his CV and a covering letter.

- a. group discussion b. shift c. application d. candidate

8. The job is mentally It needs a lot of concentration.

- a. tired b. tired c. tires d. tiring

9. We have three vacancies in Sales department. We need to three salesmen.

- a. recruit b. offer c. apply d. turn down

10. You can submit your documents to this email. But only a few candidates will be

- a. enjoy it b. headhunted c. shortlisted d. teamwork

Q. 2 You work as (a/n) accountant/ technician/ manager, etc. in a very big company. Write a paragraph on the stages of your recruitment.

Make use of some the following words: an advertisement, a local newspaper, a jobs website, applied for, CV, a covering letter, completed the application form, an interview, shortlist, referees, job offers, accept, turn down.

Good Luck😊

Q1. Encircle the best answer from (a), (b), (c), or (d) of the following to complete the sentences:

1. Azad a five-star hotel in Erbil.

- a. works by b. works from c. works on d. works for

2. My uncle a big department consisting of 20 employees.

- a. manages b. manager c. manage for d. a manager

3. That sales assistant is always He is absent three days a week.

- a. in work b. off work c. out of work d. at work

4. The librarian is not around now. She only works..... .

- a. full- time b. part- time c. shifts d. permanent

5. My brother will not resign because working there is quite

- a. dull b. tough c. routine d. satisfying

6. My sister has a baby to take care of. She is working from home. This means she is

- a. commuting b. telecommuting c. enjoys human contact d. solving problems

7. It is very nice to have a job. You can get to work whenever you want but before 11am.

- a. flexi time b. shifts c. clock in d. candidate

8. In order to apply for a job, you have to complete an

- a. application form b. CV c. covering letter d. situation vacant pages

9. After the candidates are shortlisted, we check their

- a. interviews b. job offers c. references d. group discussion

10. The company offered me a job. I have either to accept it or to

- a. enjoy it b. turn it down c. choose it d. apply for it

Q. 2 Write a paragraph on what would you like to work after graduation, or (if you work), what is your job. Make use of some the following words:

Full- time, part- time job, in charge of, one of my main responsibilities, get to work, it takes me, arrive at work, a lot of time off work.

Good Luck😊

Q. 2 You work as a salesman in a very big company. Write a paragraph on the stages of your recruitment. Make use of some the following

words: an advertisement, local newspaper, a jobs website, applied for, CV, covering letter.

Completed the application form, interview, shortlist, referees. Job offers. Accept, turn down.

Good Luck😊

Business Administration

LFU

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Q. 2 Write a paragraph on what would you like to work after graduation, or (if you work), what is your job. Make use of some the following words:

Full- time, part- time job, in charge of, one of my main responsibilities, get to work, it takes me, arrive at work, a lot of time off work.

Good Luck😊

Questions for Discussion:

1. Which one do you prefer most? A satisfying job with less salary, or a tiring one with more salary?

2. Identify three European countries that start with the letter a/i.

3. Do you like to work abroad after graduation? Why?

4. What is the most important thing you like in your future wife?

5. Do you believe in polygamy?

What is the most thing you like about management?

6. What are the most important characteristics that a manager should have?

7. If you apply for a job, what are the documents that you have to submit for application?

8. Identify three jobs that involve working from home?

9. Which one do you prefer most? A satisfying job with less salary, or hiring one with more salary? Why?

10. Identify three European countries that start with the letter a/i.

11. Do you like to work abroad after graduation? Why?

Al Salam University College

Third Year

Structural Grammar

Note: Answer FIVE questions only

Q.1 Show the immediate constituents of the following words: (10 Marks)

1. helpless
2. embodiment
3. unlawful
4. reimbursements
5. preprofessional

Q.2 Identify whether the words underlined in the following sentences are compound or grammatical structures: (10 Marks)

1. Jim's new car is a hardtop.
2. she has a strong hold on him.
3. George found his father- in- law.
4. Henry is a designing teacher. (designing is with rising- falling intonation, teacher with falling rising intonation)
5. They bought it on the black market.

Q.3 Indicate the process of word formation represented by each of the following words: (10 Marks)

1. administration
2. tick- tick
3. hiss
4. OPEC
5. smog

Q.4 Derive nouns from the following words: (10 Marks)

1. help
2. complain
3. wise
4. friend
5. contemplate
6. accept
7. coward
8. piano
9. true
10. violent

Q.5 Write grammatical sentences with the following: (10 Marks)

1. compound preposition
2. periphrastic auxiliary do
3. substitute noun
4. a qualifier that modifies an adjective
5. an article

Q.6 Show the number of morphemes each of the following words contain: (10 Marks)

1. unforgettable
2. enlargement
3. malformations
4. refertilize
5. started

Good Luck

Note: Answer FIVE questions only

Q.1 Show the immediate constituents of the following words: (10 Marks)

1. lifelessness
2. gentlemanly
3. cheerful
4. uncomfortable
5. itemized

Q.2 Identify whether the suffixes of the words underlined are ed-verbal, ed-adjectival, ing nominal, ing verbal, ing adjectival, er repetition, er noun, or er comparative (10 Marks)

1. You should read the printed statement.
2. A worried look crossed his face.
3. Old sayings are often half true.
4. A moving elephant is a picture of grace.
5. It was a charming spot.
6. The fighter weighed 100 kgs.
7. The jabber of voices came through the open door.
8. This is a heavier tennis racket than I want.

Q.3 Give the verb forms from the following adjectives: (10 Marks)

1. ripe
2. safe
3. solemn
4. solid
5. idol

Q.4 Show the grammatical structures that imply the following compound words: (10 Marks)

1. quicksand
2. outgo
3. treetop
4. stay- at- home
5. earthquake

Q.5 Give an example for each of the following word formation processes: (10 Marks)

1. reduplication
2. compounding
3. acronymy
4. clipping
5. derivation

Q.6 Underline the part of speech(structure class) in the following sentences: (10 Marks)

1. You are too tired.
2. I feel quite fine, thank you.
3. George sat between the two deans.
4. His is the best plan.
5. I think I can help you.

Good Luck

Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim

Note: Answer FIVE questions only

Q.1 Identify the number of the morphemes each of the following words contains:(10 Marks)

1. replay
2. impossible
3. unforgettable
4. biomass
5. intervene

Q.2 Identify the following words into simple, complex and compound: (10 Marks)

1. bicycle
2. purist
3. telegraph
4. football
5. pickpocket

Q.3 Give examples for each of the following processes of word formation: (10 Marks)

1. clipping
2. blending
3. compounding
4. acronymy
5. antonomasia

Q.4 Write the adverb forms derived from the following adjectives: (10 Marks)

1. fortunate
2. student
3. north

4. night
5. casual

Q.5 Identify whether the following words underlined are determiners or noun substitutes: (10 Marks)

1. His is the best plan.
2. Have you a match?
3. These are my new teammates.
4. Your slip is showing.
5. Its roof grew under the pavement.

Q.6 Show the implied grammatical structures underlying the following compound words: (10 Marks)

1. knockdown
2. afternoon
3. workman
4. rough and ready
5. killjoy

Good Luck

Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim

Note: Answer ALL questions.

Q.1 Underline the bases in the following words: (5 Marks)

1. womanly
2. befriend
3. advisor
4. successful
5. cheaper

Q.2 Draw a diagram to show the immediate constituents of the following words: (5 Marks)

1. ungentlemanly
2. insufferably
3. refertilize
4. unlawful
5. started

Q.3 Decide whether the suffixes of the following words underlined are v-al(verbal), Aj-al (Adjectival), n-al(Nominal), -er CR(Comparative), er N(Noun), or er RP(Repetition) (5 Marks)

1. We walked under the shining sun.
2. These findings surprised us.
3. The teller of this story is Ahmed.
4. The audience were impressed by the dean's speech.
5. The departed guests were our relatives.

Q.4 Add An inflectional suffix to each of the following words: (5 Marks)

1. kindness
2. arrival
3. friendly
4. popularize
5. beautify

Good Luck☺

Fourth Year

Transformational Grammar

Alsalam university

Note: Answer FIVE questions only

Q.1 Identify the three schools of Grammar and explain one of them.(10 Marks)

Q.2 Draw tree diagrams of the following sentences: (10 Marks)

1. My neighbour has seen the dog.
2. John could have been running this morning.

Q.3 Give the formulas of the following sentences, then add or delete as required between brackets, and write the resulting sentences: (10 Marks)

1. I ate then. (add be+ ing)
2. You could have been repairing the clock. (Delete be+ ing)
3. The waitress must be laughing at us. (Add have+ en)
4. We had gone to the window. (Delete have+ en)
5. I could see him well. (Delete can)

Q.4 Define the following terms in Transformational Grammar: (FIVE only)

(10 Marks)

1. PSR Phrase Structure Rules
2. TR Transformational Rules
3. PSTS Phrase Structure Terminal String
4. Concrete Nouns
5. Count Nouns
6. Competence

7. Performance
8. Intermediate Structure
9. Lexical Features
10. Lexicon

Q.5 Give the lexical features of the words underlined(nouns and verbs) in the following sentences: (FIVE only) (10 Marks)

1. Ali drives fast.
2. Mary put the book on the table.
3. The boy was lying on the floor.
4. The book dropped to the floor.
5. The ceiling leaks.
6. The camel is chewing the food.

Q.6 Give the deep structure of the following sentences using tree diagrams: (10 Marks)

1. Are you watching the clouds?
2. What did she want?
3. Don is not writing a letter.
4. We don't jump here.
5. The man is not ready now.

Q.7 Transform the following sentences into surface structures using tree diagrams: (10 Marks)

1. Q Bob will speak Adv p- wh
2. Q not he is going Adv r- wh
3. Q he wrote with NP- wh
4. Q not you have found det- wh book
5. Q she wanted NP- wh

Q.8 Answer either A or B: (10 Marks)

A. What are the four transformational processes in Transformational Grammar? Explain with examples and by using tree diagrams.

B. Transform the following sentences into surface structures using tree diagrams: (Five only)

1. Imp not you will close the door
2. I emailed a letter to my teacher (Indirect object movement)
3. I met my friend in this restaurant (Adverbial movement)
4. Q the bell present be ringing now
5. Q he present be saying NP- wh
6. Q not she arrived on time

Good Luck

Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim

Fourth Year

Transformational Grammar

Al salam university

Note: Answer FIVE questions only

Q.1 Identify the three schools of Grammar and clarify the differences among them. (10 Marks)

Q.2 Draw tree diagrams of the following sentences: (10 Marks)

1. Yes, Murphy has been very quiet.
2. The fireman will be having trouble soon.

Q.3 A. Use features to explain why the following sentences are ungrammatical. Then correct the sentences. (Five only)(10 Marks)

1. *The perseverance is a virtue.
2. *He has read book.
3. *Despair dropped to the floor.
4. *The eagle prayed for an hour.
- 5.* My boss elapsed.
- 6.* We vanished the spot.

B. What are the three components of Transformational Grammar? Explain.

Q.4 Transform the following sentences into surface structures using tree diagrams: (10 Marks)

1. not she present look tired
2. not Mary past be friendly
3. not they present have seen me here
4. not no that cat present resemble my sister's cat

Q.5 Answer either A or B of the following question: (10 Marks)

A. 1. Give the deep structure from which the following sentence is derived:

What could the man have been doing?

2. From the deep structure, give the words that are represented by the following symbols:

Aux1, V, M, be, Aux, MV, VP

B. Give the surface structure using a tree diagram and applying the transformations, if applicable, in the order: 1) negative, 2) yes no 3) wh transformation, and 4) do transformation.

1. Q the student past answer det- wh questions
2. Q the wife present can bake NP- wh

Q.6 Answer either A or B of the following questions: (10 Marks)

A What are the transformational processes in Transformational Grammar? Explain with examples.

B. Give the deep structure of the following sentences using tree diagrams (TWO only)

1. Listen to me.
2. Yesterday, I didn't know her address.
3. Someone was telling me a story.

Good Luck

Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim

Note: Answer FIVE questions only

Q.1 Answer either A or B of the following questions: (10 Marks)

A. What is the difference between structural and transformational Grammar? Explain.

B. What are the three components of Transformational Grammar? Explain.

Q.2 Write (true) opposite the sentence that matches the formula given below, and (false) opposite the sentence that does not match the formula. If the sentence does not follow the formula, give the correct formula. (Answer TWO only) (10 Marks)

1. NP+ present+ M+ V+ NP

a. The student should use the library.

b. The car will hit the child.

c. He can sing the song.

2. NP+ past+ M+ be+ NP

a. He is the owner.

b. Everybody has gone home.

c. This boy would be the winner.

3. NP+ present+ M+ have+ en+ be+ ing+ V+ place

a. John is in the train.

b. Jack will have been running in the house.

c. She must have been ill.

Q.3 Draw tree diagrams for the following sentences: (10 Marks)

1. Apparently, Tom is sick.

2. Harold might have been sitting in his room.

Q.4 Give the lexical features of the words underlined (nouns and verbs) in the following sentences: (FIVE only) (10 Marks)

1. The accident occurred yesterday.
2. Ali is editing the essay.
3. The dog barked last night.
4. Bob has handed the book to me.
5. John lurks behind the tree.
6. The spot vanished.

Q.5 Transform the following sentences into surface structures using tree diagrams and applying the transformations in the order: 1) negative, 2) yes no transformation, 3) wh-transformation, and 4) do transformation (10 Marks)

1. not of course the children past can go with us
2. Q you present be afraid
3. Q they past be singing NP-Wh
4. Q you past live Adv pl- wh
5. not you present be ready now

Q.6 Answer TWO out of the following questions (10 Marks)

A. Give the deep structure of the following sentences using tree diagrams:

1. He did not know her address yesterday.
2. Those people threw the dancer pennies.
3. Listen to me.
4. Yesterday, I could meet him.
5. Of course, the children can't go with us.

B. What is a lexicon? Give an example of a lexicon in a transformational Grammar.

C. What are the four transformational processes in Transformational Grammar? Explain with examples using tree diagrams.

Good Luck

Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim

First Year

Conversational Dialogue

Al Salam University

Note: Answer ALL questions

Q.1 Write a conversation between you and your colleague in a cafeteria. Introduce yourself, and ask about his/ her name, occupation and ask for more information like job or study. (12.5 Marks)

Q.2 You are a stranger in Beirut. Write a conversation between you and a man you met asking him how to go to the nearest shopping store. (12.5 Marks)

Q.3 What do you say in the following situations: (12.5 Marks)

- 1. Your friend liked Hong Kong. Agree with him.**
- 2. Ask about the date of your birthday.**
- 3. Ask about the opening time of the shopping store.**
- 4. Ask about the use of the key.**
- 5. Describe the clothes of your friend.**

Q.4 Fill in the blanks with suitable words and expressions you have learned: (12.5 Marks)

- A:?
B: It's Bo- wei Zhang.
- A: Does your sister have any children?
B: Yes,.....
- A: How old is your sister?
B:
- A:?

B: She's slim.

5. A: Do you know where my notebook is?

B: Yes,

Good Luck

Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim

Note: Answer ALL questions

Q.1 Write a conversation between you and your friend asking him/ her about his/ her family. Use expressions referring to the marital status, children and age. (12.5 Marks)

Q.2 Write a conversation between you and your friend asking him/ her about the likes and dislikes of London, people and food. (12.5 Mrks)

Q.3 What do you say in the following situations:(12.5 Marks)

- 1. Ask your friend about his name.**
- 2. Ask your friend about his occupation.**
- 3. Ask your friend about his/ her marital status.**
- 4. Ask your friend to describe his/ her status.**
- 5. Your friend likes Paris. Disagee with him.**

Q.4 Fill in the blanks with suitable words and expressions you have learned:(12.5 Marks)

1. A: I can't stand Chinese food.

B: Really?(Agreement)

2. A: How do you like the city?

B:

3. A:

B: Go up two blocks and turn right.

4. A: When is the party?

B: It is

5. A: What shape is the ruler?

B: It is

Good Luck

Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim

Note: Answer ALL questions

Q.1 Write a conversation between you and the librarian to apply for a library card. The librarian will ask you about your name, address, telephone, e-mail and other information. (12.5 Marks)

Q.2 It is your friend's birthday. Write a conversation to suggest him/ her to go to a festival. Include expressions about date, starting and finishing times of the festival and opening and closing times of a restaurant you will go to. (12.5 Marks)

Q.3 What do you say in the following situations: (12.5 Marks)

- 1. Ask your friend to describe the size of the mobile.**
- 2. Ask where the printer is in a formal way.**
- 3. Ask your friend about his brother's age.**
- 4. Ask about the marital status of your friend.**
- 5. Ask your friend about his last name.**

Q.4 Fill in the blanks with suitable words and expressions you have learned: (12.5 Marks)

1. A: I love this place!

B: Really?(Agreement)

2. A:Dubai?

B: I really like it.

3. A: Excuse me. Do you know where the post office is?

B: Sure. It is

4. A:your birthday?

B: It is on Monday.

5. A:

B: It is a long, narrow flat thing.

Good Luck

Teacher: Alhan Tariq Najim

Note: Answer FOUR questions only.

Q.1 Fill in the blanks to complete the following sentences:

1. A sentence is
2. The is the name of your writing.
3. The paragraph is weak or bad if
4. A is a group of words that does not have a subject nor verb or it has either a subject or verb only.
5. A should be placed before the coordinators and, but, so and yet in coordinate sentences.

Q.2 Choose the correct answer to complete the following sentences:

1. A paragraph is strong or weak if it has
 - a. one topic sentence.
 - b. one idea.
 - c. one supporting sentence.
 - d. semi colon.
2. A sentence should start with a
 - a. capital letter.

b. full stop.

c. small letter.

d. semi colon.

3. The adjective can come before the, e.g. the brilliant students.

a. noun

b. verb

c. adverb

d. preposition

4. Brainstorming by free writing means you use

a. words

b. phrases

c. short sentences

d. long sentences

5. Peer reviewing means you hand your writing to your to check it for you.

a. teacher

b. father

c. classmate

d. neighbor

Q.3 Write true if the sentence is correct, and false if it is incorrect of each of the following sentences:

1. Each paragraph should have a topic, supporting and concluding sentences.
2. A topic sentence should be the last sentence of the paragraph
3. In checking, you check whether your writing has a title, sentences are related to the topic, etc.
4. The topic that explains the topic is called supporting sentences.
5. A simple sentence should consist of two sentences combined by and or but.

Q.4 Suggest a topic sentence and concluding sentence for the following paragraph:

Steps to Follow to Use ATM

..... First, you need to insert your card into the machine to begin transaction. Second, type in your PIN. This is typically 4 digits but can be longer. Third, choose a type of transaction. Fourth, enter the transaction amount. Fifth, select your receipt preference. Finally, take your card.

..... .

Q.5 Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe ONE of the following topics:

1. your favourite place

2. you favourite person

Your writing should be about 60 words in length.

Brainstorm and write a descriptive paragraph on a piece of art you like, e.g. painting or sculpture. Your writing should be no more than 60 words in length.

Note: Answer FOUR questions only.

Q.1 Fill in the blanks to complete the following sentences: (15 Points)

1. A sentence is
2. The is the name of your writing.
3. The paragraph is weak or bad if
4. A is a group of words that does not have a subject nor verb or it has either a subject or verb only.
5. A should be placed before the coordinators and, but, so and yet in coordinate sentences.

Q.2 Choose the correct answer to complete the following sentences:

(15 Points)

1. A paragraph is strong or weak if it has
 - a. one topic sentence.
 - b. one idea.
 - c. one supporting sentence.
 - d. semi colon.
2. A sentence should start with a
 - a. capital letter.
 - b. full stop.
 - c. small letter.
 - d. semi colon.
3. The adjective can come before the, e.g. the brilliant students.
 - a. noun
 - b. verb
 - c. adverb
 - d. preposition
4. Brainstorming by free writing means you use

- a. words
- b. phrases
- c. short sentences
- d. long sentences

5. Peer reviewing means you hand your writing to your to check it for you.

- a. teacher
- b. father
- c. classmate
- d. neighbor

Q.3 Write true if the sentence is correct, and false if it is incorrect of each of the following sentences: (15 Points)

- 1. Each paragraph should have a topic, supporting and concluding sentences.
- 2. A topic sentence should be the last sentence of the paragraph
- 3. In checking, you check whether your writing has a title, sentences are related to the topic, etc.
- 4. The topic that explains the topic is called supporting sentences.
- 5. A simple sentence should consist of two sentences combined by and or but.

Q.4 Suggest a topic sentence and concluding sentence for the following paragraph: (15 Points)

Steps to Follow to Use ATM

..... First, you need to insert your card into the machine to begin transaction. Second, type in your PIN. This is typically 4 digits but

can be longer. Third, choose a type of transaction. Fourth, enter the transaction amount. Fifth, select your receipt preference. Finally, take your card.

Q.5 Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe your favourite place. Your writing should be about 60 words in length. (15 Points)

Good Luck

Instructor: Alhan T. Najim

Note: Answer FOUR questions only.

Q.1 Fill in the blanks to complete the following sentences:

1. There are six steps of writing. 1., 2., 3., 4., 5., and 6.
2. Margins means
3. A sentence should start with a and end with
4. There are four types of writing: 1., 2., 3., and 4.
5. The little boy looked so I went to comfort him.

Q.2 Choose the correct answer to complete the following sentences:

1. A coordinate sentence means
 - a. summarizing the whole paragraph.
 - b. developing the whole paragraph.
 - c. telling the reader about the topic.
 - d. explaining the topic sentence.
2. Supporting sentences
 - a. develop your topic sentence.
 - b. restate your topic sentence.
 - c. summarize the whole paragraph.
 - d. tell the reader about the topic of the paragraph.

3. A paragraph is a group of sentences that talk about one certain

- a. idea
- b. phrase
- c. topic
- d. sentence

4. A concluding sentence is the sentence that

- a. develops the topic sentence
- b. summarize the paragraph
- c. explains the topic sentence
- d. restate the topic sentence

5. capitalization is used with

- a. proper nouns
- b. coordinators
- c. articles
- d. demonstratives

Q.3 Write true if the sentence is correct, and false if it is incorrect of each of the following sentences:

- 1. A paragraph is a group of sentences that talks about many topics.
- 2. Title means the space you leave from both sides of your writing.
- 3. The descriptive paragraph tells events in a certain place and time.

4. A comma comes at the end of a sentence.
5. A simple sentence should consist of one subject and one verb.

Q.4 State whether the following paragraph is a good or bad one and give reasons for your answer:

Why do People Lie?

One reason why people lie is to achieve personal power. Achieving personal power is helpful for someone who pretends that he is more confident than he really is. For example, my friend asked me to show him my car. At that time, I did not have any car because I sold it. This is why I asked my cousin to lend me his. When I showed him my cousin's car, I felt confident but embarrassed in front of my friend but I looked down on myself. Even if lying achieves power and confidence, I decided since then not to do so.

Q.5 Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe ONE of the following topics:

1. your favourite book,
2. your favourite dish,

Your writing should be about 60 words in length.

Brainstorm and write a descriptive paragraph on a lucky object, e.g. an object that you think brings luck to your life. Your writing should be no more than 60 words in length.

Note: Answer FOUR questions only.

Q.1 Fill in the blanks to complete the following sentences: (15 Points)

1. A sentence is
2. The is the name of your writing.
3. The paragraph is weak or bad if
4. A is a group of words that does not have a subject nor verb or it has either a subject or verb only.
5. A should be placed before the coordinators and, but, so and yet in coordinate sentences.

Q.2 Choose the correct answer to complete the following sentences:

(15 Points)

1. A paragraph is strong or weak if it has
 - a. one topic sentence.
 - b. one idea.
 - c. one supporting sentence.
 - d. semi colon.
2. A sentence should start with a
 - a. capital letter.
 - b. full stop.
 - c. small letter.
 - d. semi colon.
3. The adjective can come before the, e.g. the brilliant students.
 - a. noun
 - b. verb
 - c. adverb
 - d. preposition
4. Brainstorming by free writing means you use

- a. words
- b. phrases
- c. short sentences
- d. long sentences

5. Peer reviewing means you hand your writing to your to check it for you.

- a. teacher
- b. father
- c. classmate
- d. neighbor

Q.3 Write true if the sentence is correct, and false if it is incorrect of each of the following sentences: (15 Points)

- 1. Each paragraph should have a topic, supporting and concluding sentences.
- 2. A topic sentence should be the last sentence of the paragraph
- 3. In checking, you check whether your writing has a title, sentences are related to the topic, etc.
- 4. The topic that explains the topic is called supporting sentences.
- 5. A simple sentence should consist of two sentences combined by and or but.

Q.4 Suggest a topic sentence and concluding sentence for the following paragraph: (15 Points)

Steps to Follow to Use ATM

..... First, you need to insert your card into the machine to begin transaction. Second, type in your PIN. This is typically 4 digits but

can be longer. Third, choose a type of transaction. Fourth, enter the transaction amount. Fifth, select your receipt preference. Finally, take your card.

Q.5 Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe your favourite place. Your writing should be about 60 words in length. (15 Points)

Good Luck

Instructor: Alhan T. Najim

https://forms.gle/bkPgqjridFp4qhtT9

The screenshot shows a Google Forms interface in a web browser. The browser's address bar displays the URL: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC.... The form title is "Final Exam 2020- 2021". Below the title, the form content includes:

- Section 1 of 6
- Final Exam 2020- 2021
- Al- Iraqia University
- College of Arts
- English Department
- First Classes
- Day and Evening Classes
- Note: Answer FOUR questions only..
- Email *
- Valid email address

The form is currently in a preview state, as indicated by the "Send" button and the "Questions" tab being active. The total points for the form are 125. The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows various application icons and the system clock indicating 11:31 AM on 2021/07/07.

This screenshot shows the same Google Forms page, but with the form content expanded. The "Email *" field is now a text input field with the placeholder text "Valid email address". Below this field, there is a message: "This form is collecting email addresses. [Change settings](#)".

Below the email field, there are two more text input fields:

- The first is labeled "الاسم الثلاثي:" (Last Name) and has a "Short-answer text" input field.
- The second is labeled "المرحلة و الصعبة:" (Level and Difficulty) and also has a "Short-answer text" input field.

The Windows taskbar at the bottom shows the system clock indicating 11:32 AM on 2021/07/07. A "VLC media player" window is also visible in the taskbar.

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وصاب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

Apps Suggested Sites S Google Google ترجمة 15 Make-Ahead Bre... Calorie Chart, Nutritio... Make-Ahead Instant

المرحلة و التصبة: *

Short-answer text

After section 1 Continue to next section

Section 2 of 6

Q.1 Fill in the blanks to complete the following sentences: (25 Points)

Description (optional)

11:32 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وصاب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

Apps Suggested Sites S Google Google ترجمة 15 Make-Ahead Bre... Calorie Chart, Nutritio... Make-Ahead Instant

Section 2 of 6

Q.1 Fill in the blanks to complete the following sentences: (25 Points)

Description (optional)

1. To indent means

Short-answer text

2. The type and size of of your writing should be the same in your paragraph.

11:32 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

1. To indent means

Short-answer text

2. The type and size of of your writing should be the same in your paragraph.

Short-answer text

3. The sentence should be the first or second sentence in your paragraph.

Short-answer text

11:32 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

3. The sentence should be the first or second sentence in your paragraph.

Short-answer text

4. The concluding sentence is the sentence of the paragraph.

Short-answer text

5. A concluding sentence should never tell a new about the topic.

11:32 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

5. A concluding sentence should never tell a new about the topic.

Short-answer text

After section 2 Continue to next section

Section 3 of 6

Q.2 Choose the correct answer to complete the following sentences: (25 Points)

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

Section 3 of 6

Q.2 Choose the correct answer to complete the following sentences: (25 Points)

Description (optional)

1. your writing means you should make sure whether your writing has a title, topic, supporting, etc before you hand it to your teacher.

a. brainstorming

b. checking

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

1. your writing means you should make sure whether your writing has a title, topic, supporting, etc before you hand it to your teacher.

- a. brainstorming
- b. checking
- c. peer reviewing
- d. thinking

2. Capitalization is used in the first letters of titles except

- a. conjunctions, demonstratives, articles

11:33 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

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2. Capitalization is used in the first letters of titles except

- a. conjunctions, demonstratives, articles
- b. nouns
- c. verbs
- d. adverbs

3. should be used before coordinators in coordinate sentences.

- a. full stop

11:33 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

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3. should be used before coordinators in coordinate sentences.

- a. full stop
- b. commas
- c. semi colon
- d. colon

4. Each topic sentence should have a topic and about this topic.

- a. phrase

11:34 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

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4. Each topic sentence should have a topic and about this topic.

- a. phrase
- b. opinion
- c. sentence
- d. title

5. A paragraph describes a person, a place or a thing.

- a. narrative
- b. opinion

11:34 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x واسب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC...

5. A paragraph describes a person, a place or a thing.

- a. narrative
- b. opinion
- c. descriptive
- d. explanation

After section 3 Continue to next section

Section 4 of 6

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x واسب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC...

After section 3 Continue to next section

Section 4 of 6

Q.3 Choose true if the sentence is correct and false if it is incorrect of the following sentences: (25 Points)

Description (optional)

1. A sentence is a group of words that have a subject only.

True

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

1. A sentence is a group of words that have a subject only.

True

False

2. There are two steps of writing: 1. writing and 2. post writing.

True

False

11:34 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

2. There are two steps of writing: 1. writing and 2. post writing.

True

False

...

3. The phrase should start with a capital letter and end with a full stop.

True

False

11:35 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

3. The phrase should start with a capital letter and end with a full stop.

True

False

4. A comma should come after the end of the sentence.

True

False

11:35 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

5. There are types of brainstorming by : 1. listing, 2. word map and 3. free writing.

True

False

After section 4 Continue to next section

Section 5 of 6

Q.4 What are the four types of concluding sentences? Explain with examples. (25

11:35 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

Q.4 What are the four types of concluding sentences? Explain with examples. (25 Points)

Description (optional)

Question Paragraph

Long-answer text

Answer key (25 points) Required

11:36 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

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https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

Answer key (25 points) Required

After section 5 Continue to next section

Section 6 of 6

Q.5 Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe the benefits of Learning English. Your writing should be about 60 minutes in length. (25 Points)

Description (optional)

11:37 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

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Section 6 of 6

Q.5 Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe the benefits of Learning English. Your writing should be about 60 minutes in length. (25 Points)

Description (optional)

Question

Long-answer text

11:37 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٧/٠٧

Final Exam

Iraqia University

<https://forms.gle/bkPgqjridFp4qhtT9>

<https://forms.gle/TojnSuGmpJw1zr9A>

The screenshot shows a Google Forms interface in a browser. The title is "Final Exam 2020- 2021". Below the title, the form is for "Al- Iraqia University, College of Arts, English Department, First Classes, Day and Evening Classes". A note says "Note: Answer FOUR questions only..". There is an "Email*" field with a "Valid email address" error message. The form is part of "Section 1 of 6". The browser's taskbar at the bottom shows various application icons and the system clock at 11:31 AM on 2021/07/07.

This screenshot shows a closer view of the form. The "Email*" field is highlighted with a "Valid email address" error message. Below it, a message states "This form is collecting email addresses. Change settings". There are two short-answer text questions: "الاسم الثلاثي*" (Last name) and "المرحلة و الشعبة*" (Stage and branch). The browser's taskbar at the bottom shows the system clock at 11:32 AM on 2021/07/07.

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وصاب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

Apps Suggested Sites S Google Google ترجمة 15 Make-Ahead Bre... Calorie Chart, Nutritio... Make-Ahead Instant

المرحلة و التصبة: *

Short-answer text

After section 1 Continue to next section

Section 2 of 6

Q.1 Fill in the blanks to complete the following sentences: (25 Points)

Description (optional)

11:32 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وصاب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

Apps Suggested Sites S Google Google ترجمة 15 Make-Ahead Bre... Calorie Chart, Nutritio... Make-Ahead Instant

Section 2 of 6

Q.1 Fill in the blanks to complete the following sentences: (25 Points)

Description (optional)

1. To indent means

Short-answer text

2. The type and size of of your writing should be the same in your paragraph.

11:32 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

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1. To indent means

Short-answer text

2. The type and size of of your writing should be the same in your paragraph.

Short-answer text

3. The sentence should be the first or second sentence in your paragraph.

Short-answer text

11:32 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

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3. The sentence should be the first or second sentence in your paragraph.

Short-answer text

4. The concluding sentence is the sentence of the paragraph.

Short-answer text

5. A concluding sentence should never tell a new about the topic.

11:32 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

5. A concluding sentence should never tell a new about the topic.

Short-answer text

After section 2 Continue to next section

Section 3 of 6

Q.2 Choose the correct answer to complete the following sentences: (25 Points)

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

Section 3 of 6

Q.2 Choose the correct answer to complete the following sentences: (25 Points)

Description (optional)

1. your writing means you should make sure whether your writing has a title, topic, supporting, etc before you hand it to your teacher.

a. brainstorming

b. checking

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

1. your writing means you should make sure whether your writing has a title, topic, supporting, etc before you hand it to your teacher.

- a. brainstorming
- b. checking
- c. peer reviewing
- d. thinking

2. Capitalization is used in the first letters of titles except

- a. conjunctions, demonstratives, articles

11:33 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

2. Capitalization is used in the first letters of titles except

- a. conjunctions, demonstratives, articles
- b. nouns
- c. verbs
- d. adverbs

3. should be used before coordinators in coordinate sentences.

- a. full stop

11:33 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

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3. should be used before coordinators in coordinate sentences.

- a. full stop
- b. commas
- c. semi colon
- d. colon

4. Each topic sentence should have a topic and about this topic.

- a. phrase

11:34 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

4. Each topic sentence should have a topic and about this topic.

- a. phrase
- b. opinion
- c. sentence
- d. title

5. A paragraph describes a person, a place or a thing.

- a. narrative
- b. opinion

11:34 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x واسب Final Exam 2020- 2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC...

5. A paragraph describes a person, a place or a thing.

- a. narrative
- b. opinion
- c. descriptive
- d. explanation

After section 3 Continue to next section

Section 4 of 6

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x واسب Final Exam 2020- 2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC...

After section 3 Continue to next section

Section 4 of 6

Q.3 Choose true if the sentence is correct and false if it is incorrect of the following sentences: (25 Points)

Description (optional)

1. A sentence is a group of words that have a subject only.

True

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

3. The phrase should start with a capital letter and end with a full stop.

True

False

4. A comma should come after the end of the sentence.

True

False

11:35 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

5. There are types of brainstorming by : 1. listing, 2. word map and 3. free writing.

True

False

After section 4 Continue to next section

Section 5 of 6

Q.4 What are the four types of concluding sentences? Explain with examples. (25

11:35 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x وائساب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

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Q.4 What are the four types of concluding sentences? Explain with examples. (25 Points)

Description (optional)

Question Paragraph

Long-answer text

Answer key (25 points) Required

11:36 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

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Answer key (25 points) Required

After section 5 Continue to next section

Section 6 of 6

Q.5 Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe the benefits of Learning English. Your writing should be about 60 minutes in length. (25 Points)

Description (optional)

11:37 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Final Exam

Iraqia University

<https://forms.gle/bkPgqjridFp4qhtT9>

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Section 2 of 6

Q.1 Fill in the blanks to complete the following sentences: (25 Points)

Description (optional)

1. To indent means

Short-answer text

2. The type and size of of your writing should be the same in your paragraph.

11:32 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

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1. To indent means

Short-answer text

2. The type and size of of your writing should be the same in your paragraph.

Short-answer text

3. The sentence should be the first or second sentence in your paragraph.

Short-answer text

11:32 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

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https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

3. The sentence should be the first or second sentence in your paragraph.

Short-answer text

4. The concluding sentence is the sentence of the paragraph.

Short-answer text

5. A concluding sentence should never tell a new about the topic.

11:32 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

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5. A concluding sentence should never tell a new about the topic.

Short-answer text

After section 2 Continue to next section

Section 3 of 6

Q.2 Choose the correct answer to complete the following sentences: (25 Points)

11:33 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

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Section 3 of 6

Q.2 Choose the correct answer to complete the following sentences: (25 Points)

Description (optional)

1. your writing means you should make sure whether your writing has a title, topic, supporting, etc before you hand it to your teacher.

a. brainstorming

b. checking

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https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC...

1. your writing means you should make sure whether your writing has a title, topic, supporting, etc before you hand it to your teacher.

a. brainstorming

b. checking

c. peer reviewing

d. thinking

2. Capitalization is used in the first letters of titles except

a. conjunctions, demonstratives, articles

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https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC...

2. Capitalization is used in the first letters of titles except

- a. conjunctions, demonstratives, articles
- b. nouns
- c. verbs
- d. adverbs

3. should be used before coordinators in coordinate sentences.

- a. full stop

11:33 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

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https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC...

3. should be used before coordinators in coordinate sentences.

- a. full stop
- b. commas
- c. semi colon
- d. colon

4. Each topic sentence should have a topic and about this topic.

- a. phrase

11:34 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

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After section 3 Continue to next section

Section 4 of 6

Q.3 Choose true if the sentence is correct and false if it is incorrect of the following sentences: (25 Points)

Description (optional)

1. A sentence is a group of words that have a subject only.

True

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https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC...

1. A sentence is a group of words that have a subject only.

True

False

2. There are two steps of writing: 1. writing and 2. post writing.

True

False

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https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

2. There are two steps of writing: 1. writing and 2. post writing.

True

False

3. The phrase should start with a capital letter and end with a full stop.

True

False

11:35 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

3. The phrase should start with a capital letter and end with a full stop.

True

False

4. A comma should come after the end of the sentence.

True

False

11:35 ص ٢٠٢١/٧/٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x واسب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

Apps Suggested Sites S Google Google ترجمة 15 Make-Ahead Bre Calorie Chart, Nutritio Make-Ahead Instant

Answer key (25 points) Required

After section 5 Continue to next section

Section 6 of 6

Q.5 Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe the benefits of Learning English. Your writing should be about 60 minutes in length. (25 Points)

Description (optional)

11:37 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٧/٠٧

Meet - xpg-qfxm-vrz x واسب Final Exam 2020-2021 - x

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1GvVI1DYpkKn7ps_WkTXsC... ☆

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Section 6 of 6

Q.5 Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe the benefits of Learning English. Your writing should be about 60 minutes in length. (25 Points)

Description (optional)

Question

Long-answer text

11:37 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٧/٠٧

Monthly Exam

Section 2 of 5

Q.1 Choose the correct answer of the following sentences: (4 points)

Description (optional)

a. A is a group of sentences that talks about one topic. *

- a. sentence
- b. phrase
- c. paragraph
- d. word

The screenshot shows a Google Form titled "Section 2 of 5". The question is "Q.1 Choose the correct answer of the following sentences: (4 points)". Below the question is a description field (optional). The question text is "a. A is a group of sentences that talks about one topic. *". There are four radio button options: "a. sentence", "b. phrase", "c. paragraph", and "d. word". The form is displayed in a browser window with a Windows taskbar at the bottom. The taskbar shows various application icons and the system clock indicating 07:57 on 2021/05/26.

a. A is a group of sentences that talks about one topic. *

- a. sentence
- b. phrase
- c. paragraph
- d. word

2. A sentence should start with *

- a. capital letter
- b. full stop
- c. small letter
- d. semi colon.

The screenshot shows a Google Form with two multiple-choice questions. The first question is "a. A is a group of sentences that talks about one topic. *" with options: "a. sentence", "b. phrase", "c. paragraph", and "d. word". The second question is "2. A sentence should start with *" with options: "a. capital letter", "b. full stop", "c. small letter", and "d. semi colon.". The form is displayed in a browser window with a Windows taskbar at the bottom. The taskbar shows various application icons and the system clock indicating 07:58 on 2021/05/26.

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1kNqZwBstEi8_Sm_Mp5JZfHvsKJvL5yR...
2. A sentence should start with *

- a. capital letter
- b. full stop
- c. small letter
- d. semi colon.

3. A topic sentence should include

- a. a topic and idea or opinion
- b. summary of the paragraph
- c. ideas related to the topic
- d. details

07:58 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1kNqZwBstEi8_Sm_Mp5JZfHvsKJvL5yR...
3. A topic sentence should include

- a. a topic and idea or opinion
- b. summary of the paragraph
- c. ideas related to the topic
- d. details

4. A coordinate sentence is a sentence that combine two simple sentences by a 1 points

- a. coordinator
- b. full stop
- c. subordinator
- d. question mark

07:58 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

Unit Fo x Tweets x Classw x Monthi x Classw x Blank C x

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4. A coordinate sentence is a sentence that combine two simple sentences by a 1 points

- a. coordinator
- b. full stop
- c. subordinator
- d. question mark

After section 2 Continue to next section

Section 3 of 5

Q.2 Answer with true or false the following sentences: (4 points)

Description (optional)

Unit Fo x Tweets x Classw x Monthi x Classw x Blank C x

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After section 2 Continue to next section

Section 3 of 5

Q.2 Answer with true or false the following sentences: (4 points)

Description (optional)

1. A paragraph is a group of sentences that has more than one topic. *

- a. True
- b. False

2. A concluding sentence tells a new idea about the paragraph. *

3. A should have a topic and an idea or opinion about the topic. *

Short-answer text

4. A sentence should be the last sentence in the paragraph.

Short-answer text

Answer key (1 point) Required

After section 4 Continue to next section

Section 5 of 5

Section 5 of 5

Q.4 Paragraph Writing: (4 points)

Description (optional)

Brainstorm by listing and write a paragraph to describe one of the following topics: your mobile or your day during the lockdown. Your paragraph should be around 60 words in length. *

Long-answer text

Question

Option 1

Telegram (37)

<https://forms.gle/NgVkUJW4uN225qBi7>

Monthly Exam

Section 1 of 5

Monthly Exam

Form description

After section 1 Continue to next section

Section 2 of 5

Q.2 Choose the correct answer in each of the following sentences: (4 points)

Description (optional)

Section 2 of 5

Q.2 Choose the correct answer in each of the following sentences: (4 points)

Description (optional)

1. One of the three processes of writing is post-writing which means

- a. collecting information before you start writing
- b. putting your ideas into the paper.
- c. outline
- d. checking and revising your writing

وَتَسَاب

Meet - x Unit Fo x Tweets x Classw x Monthl x Monthl x Evening x

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Apps Suggested Sites S Google Google ترجمة 15 Make-Ahead Bre Calorie Chart, Nutritio Make-Ahead Instant

1. One of the three processes of writing is post-writing which means

- a. collecting information before you start writing
- b. putting your ideas into the paper.
- c. outline
- d. checking and revising your writing

2. A sentence should start with a capital letter and end with a

- a. comma
- c. colon
- c. full stop
- d. semi colon

04:57 ص ٢٠٢١/٥/٢٦

وَتَسَاب

Meet - x Unit Fo x Tweets x Classw x Monthl x Monthl x Evening x

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Apps Suggested Sites S Google Google ترجمة 15 Make-Ahead Bre Calorie Chart, Nutritio Make-Ahead Instant

2. A sentence should start with a capital letter and end with a

- a. comma
- c. colon
- c. full stop
- d. semi colon

3. A phrase is a group of words that does not have a

Multiple choice

- a. subject or verb
- b. topic sentence
- c. supporting sentence

04:57 ص ٢٠٢١/٥/٢٦

Q.3 Suggest a topic sentence for the following paragraph: (4 points)

Description (optional)

Question *

Uses of Internet

..... Internet helps us to share information from any place in the world. Moreover, it is a source of a lot of information for education purposes. Internet enables fast transfer of news or incidents to people and it can be used for communication for the end of the world to the other. Without internet, the world would move slow nowadays.

Long-answer text

Section 3 of 5

Q.3 Suggest a topic sentence for the following paragraph: (4 points)

Description (optional)

Question *

Uses of Internet

..... Internet helps us to share information from any place in the world. Moreover, it is a source of a lot of information for education purposes. Internet enables fast transfer of news or incidents to people and it can be used for communication for the end of the world to the other. Without internet, the world would move slow nowadays.

Long-answer text

After section 3 Continue to next section

Section 4 of 5

Q.4 Paragraph Writing (4 points)

Description (optional)

Brainstorm your ideas and write a short paragraph to describe one of the followings: 1. Your mobile 2. Your favourite dish. Your writing should be about 60 words in length.

Long-answer text

الإسم الثلاثي *

Short-answer text

04:58 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

Q.4 Paragraph Writing (4 points)

Description (optional)

Brainstorm your ideas and write a short paragraph to describe one of the followings: 1. Your mobile 2. Your favourite dish. Your writing should be about 60 words in length.

Long-answer text

الإسم الثلاثي *

Short-answer text

المرحلة والشعبة *

Short-answer text

04:59 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

Section 5 of 5

Q.1 Answer with True or False the following questions: (4 points)

Description (optional)

1. Indentation means the name of the paragraph. 1 points

True

False

2. A paragraph is a group of sentences that talks about many topics. 1 points

True

False

1. Indentation means the name of the paragraph. 1 points

True

False

2. A paragraph is a group of sentences that talks about many topics. 1 points

True

False

3. A comma is used to combine two sentences before the coordinators and, and but. 1 points

True

False

4. The topic sentence should be the last sentence of the paragraph. *

<https://forms.gle/FJ4isy7ga1BrSCfq8>

Monthly Exam

*Required

Q.2 Choose the correct answer in each of the following sentences: (4 points)

3. A phrase is a group of words that does not have a * 1 point

- a. subject or verb
- b. topic sentence
- c. supporting sentence
- d. meaning

4. A topic sentence should include * 1 point

- a. a topic and idea or opinion

4. A topic sentence should include * 1 point

- a. a topic and idea or opinion
- b. summary of the paragraph
- c. ideas related to the topic
- d. details

2. A sentence should start with a capital letter and end with a * 1 point

- a. comma
- b. colon
- c. full stop
- d. semi colon

1. One of the three processes of writing is post-writing which means * 1 point

Monthly Exam

2. A sentence should start with a capital letter and end with a * 1 point

- a. comma
- b. colon
- c. full stop
- d. semi colon

1. One of the three processes of writing is post-writing which means * 1 point

- a. putting your ideas into the paper.
- b. outline
- c. checking and revising your writing
- d. collecting information before you start writing

Back Next

05:09 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

Monthly Exam

*Required

Q.3 Suggest a topic sentence for the following paragraph: (4 points)

4 points

Uses of Internet

..... Internet helps us to share information from any place in the world. Moreover, it is a source of a lot of information for education purposes. Internet enables fast transfer of news or incidents to people and it can be used for communication for the end of the world to the other. Without internet, the world would move slow nowadays.

Your answer

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VLC media player

05:10 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

Monthly Exam

*Required

Q.4 Paragraph Writing (4 points)

المرحلة و الشجة *

Your answer

الإلسم اللاللي *

Your answer

Brainstorm your ideas and write a short paragraph to describe one of the followings: 1. Your mobile 2. Your favourite dish. Your writing should be about 60 words in length. *

05:10 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

Your answer

الإلسم اللاللي *

Your answer

Brainstorm your ideas and write a short paragraph to describe one of the followings: 1. Your mobile 2. Your favourite dish. Your writing should be about 60 words in length. *

Your answer

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Google Forms

05:11 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

Unit For x Tweets x Classw x Monthl x Monthl x Evening x

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Q.4 Paragraph Writing (4 points)

المرحلة و التسمية *

aaa

الإسم الثلاثي *

najim

Brainstorm your ideas and write a short paragraph to describe one of the following: 1. Your mobile 2. Your favourite dish. Your writing should be about 60 words in length. *

Your answer

05:11 ص ٢٠٢١/٥/٢٦

Unit For x Tweets x Classw x Monthl x Monthl x Evening x

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aaa

الإسم الثلاثي *

najim

Brainstorm your ideas and write a short paragraph to describe one of the following: 1. Your mobile 2. Your favourite dish. Your writing should be about 60 words in length. *

Your answer

Back Next

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Google Forms

05:11 ص ٢٠٢١/٥/٢٦

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Form description

Email *

Valid email address

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After section 1 Continue to next section

Section 1 of 5

Section 2 of 5

Questions Responses Total points: 12

Q.2 Choose the correct answer in each of the following sentences: (4 points)

Description (optional)

1. One of the three processes of writing is post-writing which means *

- a. collecting information before you start writing
- b. putting your ideas into the paper.
- c. outline
- d. checking and revising your writing

2. A sentence should start with a capital letter and end with a *

Section 2 of 5

After section 2 Continue to next section

Section 3 of 5

Q.3 Suggest a topic sentence for the following paragraph: (4 points)

Description (optional)

Question *

Uses of Internet

..... Internet helps us to share information from any place in the world. Moreover, it is a source of a lot of information for education purposes. Internet enables fast transfer of news or incidents to people and it can be used for communication for the end of the world to the other. Without internet, the world would move slow nowadays.

05:19 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

Q.3 Suggest a topic sentence for the following paragraph: (4 points)

Description (optional)

Question *

Uses of Internet

..... Internet helps us to share information from any place in the world. Moreover, it is a source of a lot of information for education purposes. Internet enables fast transfer of news or incidents to people and it can be used for communication for the end of the world to the other. Without internet, the world would move slow nowadays.

Long-answer text

05:20 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

Section 4 of 5

Q.4 Paragraph Writing (4 points)

Description (optional)

Brainstorm your ideas and write a short paragraph to describe ONE of the following topics: 1. Your mobile 2. Your favourite dish. Your writing should be about 60 words in length.

Paragraph

Long-answer text

Answer key (0 points) Required

Telegram (37)

05:20 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

Answer key (0 points) Required

* الاسم الثلاثي:

Short-answer text

* المرحلة و النتيجة:

Short-answer text

After section 4 Continue to next section

Section 5 of 5

Q.1 Answer with True or False the following

05:20 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

Section 5 of 5

Q.1 Answer with True or False the following questions: (4 points)

Description (optional)

1. Indentation means the name of the paragraph. 1 points

True

False

2. A paragraph is a group of sentences that talks about many topics. 1 points

True

False

Telegram (37)

05:20 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

1. Indentation means the name of the paragraph. 1 points

True

False

2. A paragraph is a group of sentences that talks about many topics. 1 points

True

False

3. A comma is used to combine two sentences before the coordinators and, and but. 1 points

True

False

Telegram (37)

05:20 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

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Monthly Exam

Form description

Email *

Valid email address

This form is collecting email addresses. [Change settings](#)

After section 1 Continue to next section

Section 2 of 5

After section 1 Continue to next section

Section 2 of 5

Q.2 Choose the correct answer in each of the following sentences: (4 points)

Description (optional)

1. One of the three processes of writing is post-writing which means *

- a. collecting information before you start writing
- b. putting your ideas into the paper.
- c. outline
- d. checking and revising your writing

Section 2 of 5

Q.2 Choose the correct answer in each of the following sentences: (4 points)

Description (optional)

1. One of the three processes of writing is post-writing which means

- a. collecting information before you start writing
- b. putting your ideas into the paper.
- c. outline
- d. checking and revising your writing

2. A sentence should start with a capital letter and end with a

Telegram (37)

06:58 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

1. One of the three processes of writing is post-writing which means

- a. collecting information before you start writing
- b. putting your ideas into the paper.
- c. outline
- d. checking and revising your writing

2. A sentence should start with a capital letter and end with a

- a. comma
- c. colon
- c. full stop
- d. semi colon

06:59 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

Unit Fo x Tweets x Classwo x Monthl x Classwo x Monthl x

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2. A sentence should start with a capital letter and end with a *

- a. comma
- b. colon
- c. full stop
- d. semi colon

3. A phrase is a group of words that does not have a *

- a. subject or verb
- b. topic sentence
- c. supporting sentence
- d. meaning

Telegram (37)

06:59 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

Unit Fo x Tweets x Classwo x Monthl x Classwo x Monthl x

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3. A phrase is a group of words that does not have a *

- a. subject or verb
- b. topic sentence
- c. supporting sentence
- d. meaning

4. A topic sentence should include *

- a. a topic and idea or opinion
- b. summary of the paragraph
- c. ideas related to the topic
- d. details

06:59 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

After section 2 Continue to next section

Section 3 of 5

Q.3 Suggest a topic sentence for the following paragraph: (4 points)

Description (optional)

Question *

Uses of Internet

.....

..... Internet helps us to share information from any place in the world. Moreover, it is a source of a lot of information for education purposes. Internet enables fast transfer of news or incidents to people and it can be used for communication for the end of the world to the other. Without internet, the world would move slow nowadays.

06:59 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

Section 3 of 5

Q.3 Suggest a topic sentence for the following paragraph: (4 points)

Description (optional)

Question *

Uses of Internet

.....

..... Internet helps us to share information from any place in the world. Moreover, it is a source of a lot of information for education purposes. Internet enables fast transfer of news or incidents to people and it can be used for communication for the end of the world to the other. Without internet, the world would move slow nowadays.

Long-answer text

06:59 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

Question *

Uses of Internet

..... Internet helps us to share information from any place in the world. Moreover, it is a source of a lot of information for education purposes. Internet enables fast transfer of news or incidents to people and it can be used for communication for the end of the world to the other. Without internet, the world would move slow nowadays.

Long-answer text

After section 3 Continue to next section

Section 4 of 5

Q.4 Paragraph Writing (4 points)

Section 4 of 5

Q.4 Paragraph Writing (4 points)

Description (optional)

Brainstorm your ideas and write a short paragraph to describe ONE of the following topics: 1. Your mobile 2. Your favourite dish. Your writing should be about 60 words in length.

Long-answer text

Answer key (4 points) Required

Section 5 of 5

Q.1 Answer with True or False the following questions: (4 points)

Description (optional)

1. Indentation means the name of the paragraph. *

True

False

2. A paragraph is a group of sentences that talks about many topics. *

True

False

Telegram (37)

07:01 ص ٢٠٢١/٠٥/٢٦

1. Indentation means the name of the paragraph. *

True

False

2. A paragraph is a group of sentences that talks about many topics. *

True

False

3. A comma is used to combine two sentences before the coordinators and, and but. *

True

False

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<https://forms.gle/FJ4isy7ga1BrSCfq8>